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Understanding how home retrofit shapes indoor air quality in real homes

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Hello, I'm Dr Ciara Higham. I'm a postdoctoral researcher at the University of Sheffield working on the EPSRC Micro Network Plus, [Air Hub](#), and I am an embedded researcher at City of Doncaster Council, working within [Doncaster's Health Determinants Research Collaborator](#) (HDRC) in the Public Health team. In this role, I carry out academic research embedded in local government. My work focuses on understanding how place-based interventions, such as home retrofit programmes, can influence indoor air quality and, in turn, health outcomes. In particular, I am interested in how changes to housing (e.g. insulation, heating, and ventilation upgrades) affect indoor air quality and the environments people experience every day.

Home improvement programmes, often termed “retrofit”, are designed to make our existing homes more energy efficient and more comfortable across changing seasons. These programmes can include upgrading insulation, installing heat pumps, and improving ventilation. Alongside these benefits, it is important to understand how changes to homes can affect the air we breathe indoors.

Air quality researchers at the University’s School of Mechanical, Aerospace and Civil Engineering are collaborating with the Council’s Environmental Sustainability team to explore this question. This project brings together academic research with local knowledge of Doncaster to better understand real-world housing conditions.

Around 20 households across Doncaster are enrolled in the scheme, and residents have generously allowed us to monitor indoor environmental conditions in their homes both before and after the retrofit work takes place.

Each home has low-cost air quality sensors installed in the living room, kitchen, bedroom, and bathroom. These sensors continuously monitor parameters such as carbon dioxide, particulate matter, temperature, and humidity. This allows us to build a detailed picture of how residential indoor environments change following home improvements.

As part of this work, we are also carrying out home visits (around two hours long) using more advanced monitoring equipment to check the accuracy of the sensors, as low-cost sensor readings can drift over time. We have completed one visit per home before the retrofit work, and we will return approximately one year later to repeat these measurements. During these visits, we also explore the presence of airborne fungi by placing small plastic petri dishes filled with agar (known as settle plates) in each room. The presence of fungi is a normal feature of indoor environments. In this study, we are interested in understanding how fungal concentrations and diversity vary between homes and how this may change following retrofit work.

The close collaboration with Neighbourhood Environmental Officers has been a key strength of this work. They have built strong, trusted relationships with residents, and their involvement is central to enabling access to homes and supporting engagement. One officer, Marina Krasnakova, reflected:

“Resident engagement and trust are vital to the success of this project; without residents’ collaboration and willingness to give their time, we would not be able to carry out any aspect of the work. Working alongside the University of Sheffield in residents’ homes has been both a valuable experience and a great learning opportunity. Strong communication and flexibility from everyone involved have been key to enabling equipment calibration and the completion of surveys. I look forward to continuing our work together on this project.”

From the University perspective, this work also shows how important strong relationships are between researchers, local authority teams, and residents in making this kind of real-world monitoring possible. As [Dr Abigail Hathway](#), Senior Lecturer at the University of Sheffield and lead on the research, notes:

"In indoor air research it is essential we carry out monitoring to understand real environments, when lived in by real people. We were a team of engineers with expertise in air flows, and particle transport, but no experience of working with homes. The collaboration with HDRC Doncaster has provided us with opportunities to access real spaces, but more importantly the conversations have upskilled our researchers to enable us to do this in a safe and respectful manner, providing us with the confidence to undertake this essential work in the real world."

We are aiming to build a clear picture of how retrofit work affects indoor air quality in practice, and not just in theory. The findings from this study will help ensure that future programmes support indoor air quality, alongside energy efficiency and thermal comfort.

Interested in this work?

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